

Estimation of thallium(III) alone and in mixture with thallium(I) titrimetrically

T. Siva Rao and M. S. Prasada Rao*

Bioinorganic Chemistry Laboratories, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India

E-mail : muvvala_2000@yahoo.com Fax : 91-0891-555547

Manuscript received 30 May 2001, revised 27 September 2001, accepted 28 December 2001

The reduction of thallium(III) with glyoxal is catalyzed by light especially in the presence of bromide ions. The reaction is also catalyzed at higher temperature. Based on this reaction, a convenient method is described for the estimation of thallium(III) alone and in mixtures with thallium(I).

Recently, there has been a great need for quantitative speciation methods in order to determine labile forms of metal ions in different oxidation states. Hence, the present paper describes a convenient method for the determination of thallium(III) and for the analysis of mixtures containing thallium(III) and thallium(I).

Results and Discussion

The reaction between thallium(III) and glyoxal is slow, but is catalyzed by light. The photochemical reaction is further catalyzed in the presence of bromide¹⁻³. The reaction is also catalyzed at higher temperatures. The molar reactivity ratio of thallium(III) and glyoxal was found to be 3 : 1 as shown by the equation,

The rate of the reaction is found to increase with increasing concentration of thallium(III) up to a five-fold molar ratio of thallium(III)-to-glyoxal. But still higher ratios do not appear to further increase the reaction rate. The rate of reaction decreases with increase in perchloric acid concentration even though the potential of the $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}/\text{Tl}^{\text{I}}$ system is known to increase.

The rate of photochemical reaction is a maximum when thallium(III)-to-bromide ratio is in the range 10 : 1 to 1 : 1. Under these conditions Tl^{III} is known to exist as TlBr^{2+} and is responsible for the fast reaction, and the electron transfer occurs probably through the formation of a similar bridge-activated complex proposed earlier^{3,4}.

Estimation of Tl^{III} with glyoxal (mmol range) :

Photochemical method : To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.50 mmol of Tl^{III} , were added perchloric acid/sulfuric acid (5.0 ml of 5.0 mol dm^{-3}), bromide (0.05 mmol) and glyoxal (2.5 mmol) and dilute to 50 ml. The solution was stirred and exposed to the radiation from a high pressure mercury vapor lamp for 30 min. Then conc. HCl (10 ml) and 0.1%

methyl orange indicator (0.01 ml) were added and heated to 60° and titrated with 0.025 mol dm^{-3} potassium bromate until the indicator was destroyed. The recovery data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Estimation of Tl^{III} by glyoxal photochemical method

Amount of Tl^{III} = 0.05–0.50 mmol, amount of glyoxal = 2.5 mmol, concn. of HClO_4 = 5 ml of 5.0 mol dm^{-3} , total volume of reaction mixture = 50 ml

Amount of Tl^{III} (mmol)		% Error
Taken	Found	
0.050	0.050	Nil
0.055	0.055	Nil
0.065	0.064	1.5
0.090	0.090	Nil
0.095	0.096	1.1
1.000	1.000	Nil
0.256	0.250	2.4
0.450	0.450	Nil
0.500	0.500	Nil

Table 2. Estimation of Tl^{III} by glyoxal thermal method

Amount of Tl^{III} (mmol)		% Error
Taken	Found	
0.050	0.050	Nil
0.055	0.055	Nil
0.060	0.061	1.7
0.090	0.090	Nil
0.095	0.095	Nil
1.000	0.099	1.0
0.250	0.249	0.4
0.350	0.350	Nil
0.450	0.448	0.4
0.500	0.500	Nil

Table 3. Estimation of Tl^{III} and Tl^I in a mixture

Amount Taken (mmol)		Amount Found (mmol)		% Error	
Tl^{III}	Tl^I	Tl^{III}	Tl^I	Tl^{III}	Tl^I
0.050	0.025	0.050	0.025	Nil	Nil
0.100	0.037	0.098	0.037	1.3	Nil
0.150	0.050	0.148	0.050	1.3	Nil
0.200	0.050	0.200	0.049	Nil	2.0
0.250	0.075	0.248	0.074	1.3	1.3
0.300	0.012	0.297	0.012	0.8	Nil

Thermal method : To an aliquot containing 0.05–0.50 mmol of Tl^{III} , 5.0 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid (5ml) and glyoxal (2.5 mmol) were added and diluted to 50 ml and refluxed for 60 min. Then conc. HCl (10 ml) was added to it, heated to 60° , 0.1% methyl orange indicator (0.1 ml) was added and titrated with $0.025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ potassium bromate until the indicator was destroyed. The recovery data are presented in Table 2.

Determination of Tl^{III} and Tl^I in a mixture :

The thallimetric oxidation method was applied to the analysis of mixtures of Tl^I and Tl^{III} . Two identical aliquots of the sample were taken. Tl^I content in the first one was determined directly by a bromatometric method. The second aliquot was mixed with glyoxal and perchloric acid and either refluxed for 60 min or, in the presence of bromide,

exposed to radiation from a high pressure mercury vapor lamp for 30 min. The total Tl^I was then determined by titration with bromate. The first titration gave the amount of Tl^I and second one gave total amount of Tl^I . The amount of Tl^{III} was obtained by difference. The recovery data are given in Table 3.

Experimental

Thallium(III) solution was prepared in perchloric acid medium and standardized as reported earlier^{1,5}.

The photochemical reaction was performed using a Philips high-pressure mercury vapor lamp (200/250 V, 125 W) as the light source, placed 15 cm above the test solutions contained in colourless uncovered glass (Corning) vessels.

References

1. S. R. Sagi, G. S. P. Raju, K. A. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 413.
2. S. R. Sagi, K. A. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, **61**, 2795; M. S. P. Rao, A. R. M. Rao, K. V. Ramana and S. R. Sagi, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 753.
3. K. S. Gupta and Y. K. Gupta, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 2000.
4. M. S. P. Rao, A. R. M. Rao, R. Kalavathi, T. S. Rao and P. Vani, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 2283.
5. S. R. Sagi and K. V. Ramana, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 1217.